

grown after gram, lucerne, and wheat did not differ but a significant difference in nitrogen requirement was observed. However, kharif rice crop required 30 kg N/ha less when grown after gram and lucerne than after wheat.

Results suggest that biological nitrogen fixation by dubari crops after kharif rice benefits growth and grain yield of the next rice crop. ♪

Effect of nitrogen fertilizer on grain yield of kharif rice grown after dubari crops.

Announcements

Activities of the IRRI Japan Library Office

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Japanese scientists contributed about one-fourth of the world literature on rice that was cataloged in the 1979 International Bibliography of Rice Research (IBRR), published by the IRRI Library (see figure). About 80% of these materials are in Japanese, which reduces their impact on international agriculture. In anticipation of this shortcoming the IRRI Tokyo Office (now the Japan Office) at the National Institute of Agricultural Sciences was concurrently established with IRRI.

The Japan Office screens, collects, indexes, and translates published and

unpublished Japanese materials about rice research. Translating complete books on rice in cooperation with Japanese authors and researchers and writing English annotations of other works are an important function of the office.

More than 67,942 Japanese references were included in the IBRR between 1951 and 1979. All publications cited in the IBRR are available at the IRRI library and copies of IBRR have been distributed to the libraries of major universities and institutes associated with rice research throughout the world.

Since 1961 the Japan Office has translated 900 books and articles from Japanese to English. Translations are available at the IRRI library, the translation center of the John Crerar Library in Chicago, Illinois, USA, and the Japan Office. Lists of translations are in IBRR supplements published since 1964. ♪

Ratio of the number of publications written by Japanese scientists to the world rice literature.

New IRRI publications

New IRRI publications are available for purchase from the Information Services Department, Division C, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines:

- A global experiment in agricultural development*
- An adventure in applied science: a history of the International Rice Research Institute*
- A methodology for on-farm cropping systems research*
- Fundamentals of rice crop science*
- Landless workers and rice farmers: peasant subclasses under agrarian reform in two Philippine villages*

- Major weeds of rice in South and Southeast Asia*
- Manual for testing insecticides on rice*
- Proceedings of the 1981 International Deep-water Rice Workshop*
- Research highlights for 1981*
- Rice research strategies for the future*
- The role of anthropologists and other social scientists in interdisciplinary teams developing improved food production technology* ♪